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Social Adjustment and Emotional Intelligence as Determinants of Deviant Behaviour among Undergraduates

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ABSTRACT

Deviant Behaviour has been researched on over time. Despite this, factors that really influence the above variable have not reached agreement among researchers. Past researches have shown the deviant behaviour among undergraduates as a major challenge which could debar them from making progress in their educational pursuit. This study, which adopted a descriptive survey, was designed to investigate the role of social adjustment, Self-Regulation, Self-Awareness and Internal Motivation on deviant behavior among undergraduates of University of Ibadan. The population of this study comprised all undergraduates of University of Ibadan. A sample of two hundred and fifty (250) students was randomly selected from four faculties for the study using simple random technique. Three research questions were raised using multiple regression analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between the social adjustment ($r = .560$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$), Self-Regulation ($r = .488$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$), Self-Awareness ($r = .459$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$), Internal Motivation ($r = .427$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$) and deviant behavior. It was also discovered that the independent variables jointly accounted 31% variance in predicting deviant behaviour in the following order: Social Adjustment ($\beta = 0.467$, $t = 4.965$, $P < .05$, Self-Regulation ($\beta = 0.136$, $t = 3.125$, $P > .05$), Self-Awareness ($\beta = 0.115$, $t = 1.092$, $P > .05$), and Internal Motivation ($\beta = 0.125$, $t = 2.161$, $P > .05$). This implies that social adjustment is a compelling factor on the deviant behavior among undergraduates while emotional intelligence is not a potent determinant of deviant behaviour among undergraduates of University of Ibadan. Based on this, it is expected that teachers and stakeholders should wage war against any form of deviant behaviours in schools, as that can tarnish the image of a school if not properly handled. More so, schools should create a friendly environment that will enhance social adjustment among students as that also can help in minimizing the extent of deviant behaviours among students, thereby boosting the image of our dear country, Nigeria.

Keywords: Social adjustment, Emotional intelligence, Deviant behaviour, Social adjustment, Social regulation

INTRODUCTION

Social norms differ throughout society and between cultures. A certain act or behaviour may be viewed as deviant and receive sanctions or punishments within one society and be seen as a normal behaviour in another society. Additionally, as a society's understanding of social norms changes over time, so too does the collective perception of deviance. Laughing out loud might not be considered deviant for a group of partygoers at a comedy club, but it would be at a funeral. What is deviant for one person or group may not be for another and a deviance in one situation may not be in another. No consensus reliably identifies behaviour, people, or conditions that are deviant, although most people would say that they know deviance when they see it. Many lists would include mental disorder, suicide, crime, homosexuality and alcoholism.

Idris et al. (2017) defined deviance as any behaviour that does not follow expected rules, beliefs and norms according to the established standard of the society. A study has indicated that being a child, their environment and especially their family are the most significant influences that can shape adolescents personalities. (Zaky, 2017)

What can be noticed in schools these days are cases of indiscipline such as lateness, truancy, disobedience to teachers, beating of junior students, stealing, rape, extortion of money from junior ones, wearing of assorted dresses apart from school uniform, smoking, drug abuse, drinking and other adolescents' deviant behaviours among students (Achimugu, 2005). Deviant behaviour by teenagers includes antisocial, delinquent, wrongful, aggressive, self-destructing, and suicidal acts. These acts may lead to various abnormalities in personal development. Often these deviations include children's reactions to the difficult life circumstances (Wolfe, Marcum, Higgins & Ricketts, 2014). This condition often ranges from facets of disease to norm. Therefore, it should be evaluated by both a teacher and a doctor.

Furthermore, deviance exists wherever human beings live in groups. That is the period that lies between end of the childhood and the beginning of adulthood. On the other hand, deviant behavior is considered abnormal or antisocial if it is uncommon, different from the normal and does not conform needed expectations of the society. For example, recently, an increasing number of North American youths are committing violent crimes. Although the consequences of these violent crimes are easily apparent, the causes behind them are often abstract and obscure, making it difficult to pin blame on a single source.

Goleman (1998) as cited in Terfessa (2014), referred emotional intelligence as the ability to be aware of one's emotions and managing those emotions in the daily interactions with people, to establish emotional connections. He also claims that by the understanding and managing of one's emotions, the more one will be able to communicate one's feeling in a more constructive way. An individual with high EI is not only aware of what emotions they are feeling but can put words to their feelings. They can also understand the consequences of their emotions and how they may change and shift over time. Once a person has achieved the first component, they can move on to self-regulation. An individual with a good awareness of their own emotions can better manage the emotions and behaviours that come along with them. This may involve noticing a difficult emotion and slowing down or resisting any impulsive action that may follow. Emotional self-regulation is a skill that people learn and develop throughout childhood and adolescence and into adulthood. Feeling strong emotions is healthy. Learning how to process emotions and respond with appropriate behavior is essential to a person's well-being. Lacking emotional self-regulation can perpetuate negative emotions. It can also have social repercussions, such as damaging relationships with others. This happens when a person chooses to step back from an emotionally triggering situation and reframe it in a way that changes its emotional impact. Cognitive reappraisal happens before a person becomes charged with emotion.

Furthermore, self-awareness is the ability of an individual to perceive and understand his or her own moods and motivations and their effect on others. For Instance, when an individual from a poor background is able to perceive and understand the type of background he/she has come from, what is expected of him/her from the parents and society, then such an individual will be able to avoid any form of deviant behaviour that endanger his future and make him/her not to achieve what is expected of him/her by the society.

To this end, Chinelo (2011) rightly pointed that schools should facilitate seminars, conferences and orientation programme to freshers on the implications of deviant behaviours in schools

Statement of the Problem

It is obvious that the deviant behaviours of some students especially university students has put questions on the mouth of parents, teachers, stakeholders and even the students on what might be the contributing effect of such menarche. Students no longer regard good and well-mannered form of behaving and as such sees it as old fashioned form of behavior. It is therefore imperative to say that deviant behavior is now a trend; most students now prefer to go half naked instead of dressing decently, in fact, decent dressing according to most of them is now out of fashion and this is gradually crippling the moral aspect of our cultures. More so, individuals especially students no longer want to live according to what they have in their pocket, thereby making them to engage in all manner of behaviour such as arm robbery and prostitution which is also considered as a deviant behavior.

More so, deviant behaviours have crippled into our institutions of learning, examination malpractice which should be seen as evil have now been seen as a good thing by most student. Smoking, indecent dressing and violence has also become a persistent event in most of the tertiary institutions, all these, have become a contributing factor in the manifestation of deviant behavior among students. Cultism has become a thing to be feared in most tertiary institutions instead of the cultist to fear the authority, the authority are now the ones scared of the secret cults because they are fully armed with ammunition as some of them are from a wealthy family. It has also been observed that some of these secret cults no longer portray themselves as secret cults but rather as a club where they actualize their evil mission. All these have contributed to the persistent increase in deviant behaviour of students in tertiary institutions; this then has led to this research work which tends to find out how the social adjustment self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation of students can be a determining factor in the manifestation of deviant behaviour among undergraduate's students.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research work includes:

1. Investigate the relationship that exists among the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates of University of Ibadan.
2. Examine the joint contribution that exists among each of the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates of University of Ibadan.
3. Find the relative contribution of each of the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates of University of Ibadan.

Research Questions

1. What is the pattern of relationship of each of the independent variables (Social adjustment and emotional intelligence) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates?
2. What is the joint contribution of each of the independent variables (social adjustment and emotional intelligence) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates?
3. What is the relative contribution of each of the independent variables to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates?

Population

The population of this study comprised all undergraduates of University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Design

The design used for the study is a descriptive research design of correlational type. This is to investigate the relationship of social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation on the manifestation of deviant behavior among undergraduates of University of Ibadan.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study comprised of Two hundred and fifty (250) undergraduates. Four Faculties out of thirteen were used for the study and the faculties were: Faculties of Education (74 Undergraduates), Social Sciences (60 undergraduates), Sciences (59) and Arts (57 undergraduates)

Instrumentation

The instrument used for the collection of data were Deviant Behaviour Scale (DBS). Social Adjustment Scale (SAS) and Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQUE).

Deviant Behaviour Scale (DBS)

Deviant Behaviour Scale was an initial pool of a 34 items out of which 25 items was drafted for the study. The scale was compiled from literature review on pre-existing self-reported measures of delinquent behaviour by Bendixen and Olweus 1999, Junger-Tas 2003, Smith and Mevie 2003.

Items had different severity levels and pertained to 11 categories such as thefts, alcohol and drug consumption, verbal and physical aggression, possession of weapons, vandalism, truancy, lies and defiance of authority. Overall, the scale presented good psychometric properties, which results in 0.72 as the reliability and 0.74 supporting that the deviant behavior scale is a valid and reliable measure. However, the scale was pilot tested on 20 respondents which yielded a cronbach alpha of 0.85.

Social Adjustment Scale (SAS)

Social Adjustment Scale was developed by Baker and Siryk (1989). The scale was designed as a five likert type. The determination of the reliability is one major steps during the construction of the scale. For determining the reliability of the SAS, the scores of the odd and the even items were taken separately on a sample of 457 subjects. The product moment correlation co-efficient thus was 0.853. The validity of scale was assessed by finding correlations between total scale and the score on each item using product moment method. Computed values of Pearson 'r' ranged from .168 to .505 (correlation co-efficient significant at .01 levels). However, the pilot testing carried out on 20 respondents yielded a cronbach alpha of 0.84.

Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQUE)

TEIQUE was developed by Petrides (2003). It comprised of 15 items designed to measure global trait emotional intelligence (trait EI). However, this scale was divided into three components which are self-awareness, self-regulations and internal motivation. The internal consistencies of the TEIQUE was 0.76 while the pilot testing carried out on 20 respondents on self-awareness yielded a cronbach alpha of 0.76, self-regulation yielded a cronbach alpha of 0.85 while internal motivation yielded a cronbach alpha of 0.70

Procedure for Data Collection

The questionnaire was taken to University of Ibadan by the researchers. The field work was carried out within two weeks. Students were randomly selected in the administration of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed by the researcher and collected the same day. The instruction to be followed and a brief discussion were also given by the researchers and the students were given enough time to respond to the questionnaire.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the significant relationship between each of the independent variables and dependent variable. While Multiple Regression Analysis was used in order to analyze the joint and relative effect of the independent variables (social adjustment and emotional intelligent) on the influence of dependent variable (Deviant Behavior),

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between the independent variables (Social Adjustment, Self-Regulation, Self-Awareness and Internal Motivation) and the dependent variable (Deviant Behaviour) among undergraduate?*

Table 1: Summary of Correlations among Independent Variable and Deviant Behaviour

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Deviant behaviour	Social adjustment	Self regulation	Self-awareness	Internal motivation
Deviant Behaviour	44.86	12.99492	1				
Social adjustment	45.86	15.45958	.560**	1			
Self-regulation	14.60	5.31255	.488**	.817**	1		
Self-awareness	14.16	5.18400	.459**	.712**	.802**	1	
Internal Motivation	14.20	5.43305	.427**	.693**	.734**	.811**	1

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)**

Table 1 reveals the inter-correlation matrix of the significant relationship among the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the prediction of deviant behavior of the participants. The results shows significant relationship among the independent variables to deviant behavior as follows; social adjustment ($r = .459$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$), self-regulation ($r = .488$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$), self-awareness ($r = .459$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$) and internal motivation ($r = .427$, $N = 250$, $P < .05$). This indicates that social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation have significant relationship with deviant behavior. More so, this result indicates that the higher the emotional intelligence of an individual, the lower the tendency of such an individual to engage in any form of deviant behavior.

Research Question Two: *What is the joint contribution of each of the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) on the dependent variable (deviant behaviour) among undergraduates?*

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis showing Joint Contribution of Independent Variable to the Prediction of Deviant Behaviour among Undergraduates.

R = .567					
R Square = .321					
Adjusted R Square = .310					
Standard Error of Estimate = 10.79181					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	28533.489	4	3378.653	29.010	.000 ^b
1. Residual	13514.611	245	116.463		
Total	42048.100	249			

Dependent Variable: Deviant Behaviour

Table 2 indicates the prediction of all the independent variable. Deviant behavior correlated positively with the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation). The table also revealed a coefficient of multiple correlation (R) of 0.567 and a multiple adjusted R square of .321. This means that 31% of the variance in the deviant behavior is accounted for by social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation when taken together. The significant f the composite contribution was tested at $p < 0.05$ F-ratio (29.010) at the degree of freedom (df

= 2/245). This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this study may have accounted for the remaining variance.

Research Question Three: *What is the relative contribution of each of the variable on the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among undergraduates?*

Table 3: the Relative Contribution of each of the Independent Variables to Deviant Behaviour among the Participants

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	22.269	2.233		9.973	.000
Social Adjustment	.393	.792	.467	4.965	.000
Self-Regulation	.334	.267	.136	3.125	.009
Self-Awareness	.288	.264	.115	1.092	.028
Internal motivation	.230	.225	.125	2.161	.009

a. Dependent Variable: Deviant Behaviour

Result from Table 3 reveals relative contribution of the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the dependent variable (deviant behavior) among University of Ibadan undergraduates. In terms of the magnitude of the contribution: Social adjustment contributed most to the prediction of deviant behavior among the undergraduate. ($\beta = 0.467$, $t = 4.965$, $P < .05$), followed by self-regulation ($\beta = 0.136$, $t = 3.125$, $P > .05$), internal motivation ($\beta = 0.125$, $t = 2.161$, $P > .05$) and self-awareness ($\beta = 0.115$, $t = 1.092$, $P > .05$). This implies that social adjustment is a compelling factor that contributed more to the deviant behavior among undergraduates.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The result of the findings obtained from research question one showed a significant relationship among the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the prediction of deviant behavior of participants. The findings of this work is consistent with the findings of Ezeugwu, (2013) who found that student adjustment to school helps to prevent delinquent acts in the students. This implies that social adjustment has a significant influence on the exhibition of deviant behavior among undergraduates. Thus, a number of studies report that students' involvement in deviant behavior can hamper their adjustment in school.

Rahman, 2012 and Jean 2010, reported that deviancy at the university level is as a result of students not connecting socially in the academic environment and not gaining membership into the campus community which therefore hampers full social integration into the university system, thereby leading to withdrawal amongst the students. Rozell, Pettijohn, and Parker, (2006) found that high emotionally intelligent students find practical ways to overcome delinquent behavior in carrying out some tasks for the achievement of a set goal. In addition, evidence has accumulated that emotional intelligence is a distinct measure in curbing deviant behavior (Brackett & Mayer, 2003; Ciarrochi, Chan, Caputi & Roberts, 2001; Mayer, Salovey, Caruso, & Sitarenios, 2003).

Hogan and Majeki (2004) stated that the level of intelligence of a learner helps in curbing any form of delinquent act in such an individual as that will help the students in identifying consequences that will follow any behavior the student engages in. Further studies suggest that lower EI (Emotional Intelligence) is related to involvement in self-destructive behaviour such as deviant behavior and smoking (Brackett & Mayer, 2003; Rubin, 1999, Trinidad & Johnson, 2001), whereas higher EI is related to positive outcomes

such as prosocial behavior, parental warmth, and positive peer and family relations (Mayer 1999, Rice, 1999; Salovey, Mayer, Caruso, & Lopes, 2001).

Avolio and Gardner, (2005) stated that self-regulation is the process through which authentic learners align their values with their intentions and actions. Key to this concept is that the regulatory system is internally driven, not a reaction to external forces or expectations. Furthermore, self – regulation is distinct from concepts such as self-monitoring or impression management, which can encompass purposively distorted communications and therefore lead to inauthentic dialogue. Rather, self-regulation involves establishing congruence between one’s internal standards and anticipated outcomes which can curb any form of deviance (Gardner et al, 2005).

In the view of Goleman (2006), self-

In the view of Goleman (2006), self- awareness refers to the ability of an individual to identify their internal states, preferences, resources and effects. According to the author, self-awareness also involves the ability of an individual to accurately engage in self-assessment. This means knowing one’s emotional state and their effects. The individual at the same time should be able to manifest some level of self-confidence, which means being sure of their strengths and limitations. Agulanna and Nwachukwu (2017) chose to view self-awareness in relation to intrapersonal intelligence. The duo described this as the capacity the individual demonstrates by being able to adapt to the environment, themselves and the dynamic situations in and around subsequently. Critically looking at the above definitions, self-awareness could summarily be perceived in terms of the capacity of an individual to understand their authentic self. The individual in other words perceives themselves as realistic as possible.

Emotional intelligence that is speculated to foster fresh students’ academic adjustment. This element in question is self-regulation. In line with the above, Goleman (2006) maintained the opinion that self-regulation is the emotional maturity that is consistent in the ability of the individual to own up responsibility for their actions. Continuing, the author believes it is the ability of the individual to adapt to changes and the ability also to demonstrate appropriate understanding and response to neighbors’ irrational or unreasonable emotions or behaviours. One component that is yet linked with self-regulation, which contributes essentially to the success of the individual both in and outside the school, is self-motivation.

The understanding of the term internal-motivation will be enhanced by the clear meaning and knowledge of the word motivation. The term motivation is a psychological construct. It can be described as the active, energizing drive that galvanizes an individual who is in need and desires to actualize the need to pursue and achieve the desired need. This drive enables the individual to be focused in the pursuit to achieve their dreams. Thus, an individual can be internally-motivated in their drive to actualize their potential. In this study internal -motivation is considered as yet another emotional intelligence factor which builds up diligent skill, the skill of resilience, the ability and determination to be focused in the attainment of (desired) potentials. In this way, individuals who possess a high internal-motivation level tend to organize constructive goals for themselves to guide the final actualization of their potential and as well as be able curb any maladaptive and deviant behaviour that may want to arise.

The result of the study obtained from research question two, showed a significant correlation of each of the independent variables (social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation) to the dependent variable (deviant behaviour). In essence, this implies that as students adjust socially to the demands of university life as well as have a high emotional intelligence, the extent of deviant behavior among students will be reduced. This is in line with the findings of Harper (1990 as cited in Rahman, 2012) found that 33% to 75% of tertiary students who have engaged in most deviant behaviours such as vandalism, violence, unwanted absenteeism, and examination malpractice, to mention but a few, is as a result of inadequate adjustment to the rules and regulations governing a school.

From the result of the study obtained from research question three stated that social adjustment is a potent predicting factor of deviant behavior among undergraduates while component of emotional intelligence were not a strong predictor of deviant behavior among undergraduates of University of Ibadan. Thus, this is in line with the findings of Ogidefa (2008) which stated that there is hardly any single Nigerian institution of higher learning that has not experienced this menace of cultism which is also a form of

deviancy. Levine (2007) also found that there has being a significant increase in violent youth crime which African has not been an exception due to the increasing economic hardship and recession experienced in many part of the region. Abdullah (2006) also found that some dimensions of emotional intelligence significantly predict academic performance than deviant behavior among undergraduates.

CONCLUSION

The researchers concluded that social adjustment, self-regulation, self-awareness and internal motivation are the determinants of deviant behaviour among undergraduates of university of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Parents, Counsellors, Teachers, and relevant stakeholder should motivate students on the need to abstain from any form of deviancy such as cultism, gambling, clubbing etc. which could serve as a threat to the realization of their set goal in life.
- Teachers should encourage students on the need to be of good conduct and behavior.
- Counselors in school should always from time to time organize seminars on the dangers of deviant behavior as that will serve as an eye opener to the students.
- School management should ensure that offenders (those that engage in deviant behaviour) are punished irrespective of class or position as that also will help to serve as a warning to others.
- Workshop and group discussion on dangers of deviant behavior should be organized for students' to boost and enhance their residual understanding of this factors and enlightening them on how to avoid any form of deviance.
- Teachers, counselors and school administrators should work towards improving a friendly environment for learning as that will enhance adjustment which can also help in curbing any form of deviancy on the part of the students.
- Government, policy makers and all other stakeholders in education are to ensure enough security personnel in schools that could also assist in manipulation peace and tranquility in our higher institutions of learning.

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